

BENDING STRENGTH AND MODULUS OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

BY MEANS OF COMPRESSION BENDING

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with a new bending test method of advanced composites. Although a conventional three- or four-point bending test is convenient to obtain bending modulus and strength, composites may fail at the loading nose because composite materials have high anisotropy and they fail in a brittle manner.

To compensate for the above shortcoming, we developed a new bending test method[1] which is based on a kind of buckling.

In the present paper, a methodology to evaluate the bending modulus is discussed in addition to the bending strength. T300 and T800 carbon/epoxy laminates with some specimen lengths were tested. The superiority of the present method was demonstrated especially for composites made of extremely high strength fibers such as T800 carbon fiber.

1. INTRODUCTION

In these years advanced composite materials are widely used especially for aerospace applications. New fibers with very high performance are also being developed. For example, T800 carbon fiber of Toray Industries has the tensile strength of 5GPa, which is already available commercially. High modulus carbon fibers have also been developed. New materials require new testing methods.

A three- or four-point bending test is commonly used to evaluate the bending strength of the advanced composites. Although this kind of test is easy to operate, it includes some disadvantages as was discussed in Ref.[1].

In the previous paper, we proposed a new bending test method which was named a compression bending. In that paper we focused only on the bending strength and no discussion was made for bending modulus.

Recently we have found that the bending modulus can also be evaluated by means of this compression bending. In the present paper, a scheme to evaluate the bending modulus is described. Experimental data are compared with the values of conventional four-point bending. Bending strength is also described as a reference.

2. PRINCIPLE OF COMPRESSION BENDING

Consider a bar with rectangular cross section (width= b , thickness= t) and both ends being pin supported. When some compressive axial load, P , is applied to it, the bar will deform. Figure 1 demonstrates a half part of the specimen. Bending strength and modulus can be calculated as follows.

2.1 Bending Strength

The bending strength is considered first. Denoting the deflection at midspan A of Fig.1 as δ_A , the bending moment at point A becomes

$$M_A = P\delta_A \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load. Then the bending stress (skin stress) at point A is, under the assumption of linear elasticity,

$$\sigma_A = \frac{6M_A}{bt^2} \quad (2)$$

and the bending strength, F_A , can be calculated as

$$F_A = \frac{6M_{\max}}{bt^2} \quad (3)$$

where M_{\max} is the bending moment at failure. Thus by measuring P and δ_A at failure, bending strength can be calculated.

2.2 Bending Modulus

Let's consider now the bending modulus. According to the strength of materials,

$$\frac{EI}{\rho} = M \quad (4)$$

holds where E is Young's modulus, I is the moment of inertia of section, and ρ is the radius of curvature. Substituting eq.(1) into eq.(4), Young's modulus is calculated as

Fig.1 Schematic view of compression bending

Fig.2 Overview of test

$$E = \frac{P\delta_A \rho_A}{I} \quad (5)$$

Then if we measure P , δ_A , ρ_A and I , the bending modulus can be calculated. In the following, we tried two methods to measure or to calculate δ_A and ρ_A , which are called here (a) strain gage method and (b) elastica method.

2.2.1 strain gage method

Denoting the skin strains on both surfaces of the specimen as ϵ_t (tension) and ϵ_c (compression) and assuming Euler-Bernoulli hypothesis, the radius of curvature is calculated by

$$\rho = \frac{t}{\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c} \quad (6)$$

In the strain gage method, strain gages are attached on both surfaces of the specimen at mid point A of Fig.1, from which ρ_A can be calculated. The deflection δ_A is also necessary to measure individually. Figure 2 is the set-up of the test devices which has already been reported in Ref.[1].

2.2.2 elastica method

According to the elastica theory[3], the crosshead movement λ , deflection δ_A and the radius of curvature ρ_A of Fig.1 can be calculated as a function of the angle of deflection at the loading point, α . These are, after some calculation,

$$\frac{\lambda}{L} = 4-4 \frac{E(p)}{K(p)} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\delta}{L} = \frac{2p}{K(p)} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\rho}{L} = \frac{1}{2pK(p)} \quad (9)$$

where

$$p = \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (10)$$

$$K(p) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-p^2 \sin^2 \phi}} d\phi \quad (11)$$

$$E(p) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1-p^2 \sin^2 \phi} d\phi \quad (12)$$

$K(p)$ and $E(p)$ are known as the first and second perfect elliptical integrals. Equations (7)-(9) show that λ/L , δ/L and ρ/L are independent of material constants and specimen geometry and they are functions of only α . Therefore,

prior to the experiment, values of eqs.(7)-(9) were calculated at various angle α . Figure 3 shows the relation between δ/L and λ/L . Dots are theoretical values of the present concern. Circles will be described later. Similarly, Fig.4 is the $\rho/L - \lambda/L$ plots.

Fig.3 δ/L vs. λ/L curve

Fig.4 ρ/L vs. λ/L curve

Table 1 Materials used for the test

fiber	matrix	stacking seq.	notation	thick.
Torayca T800 ^H	177°C cure epoxy 3631	(0) ₁₆	U8	2.24
		(0/±45/90) _{2S}	Q8	2.22
Torayca T300	177°C cure epoxy 3601	(0) ₁₆	U3	2.16
		(0/±45/90) _{2S}	Q3	2.21

V_f=60% nominal
cure: autoclave, non-bleed processing

Thus in the elastica method, what we need to measure are only the applied load P and the crosshead movement λ. Test devices become much simpler than Fig.2 because we don't have to measure the deflection, δ.

Since no loading device is attached at the location of the maximum bending moment, the stress concentration due to the loading nose does not occur. This will result in the improvement of the bending strength.

3. TEST PROCEDURE

3.1 Test Specimen

Specimens tested here are advanced composites with unidirectional prepreg sheets of Toray T300 and T800 carbon fiber. Tensile strengths of these fibers are about 3GPa and 5GPa, respectively. The matrix is 177 C cure epoxy resin. Laminated plates were made in an autoclave. Both unidirectional and quasi-isotropic specimens were tested. A summary of the materials is shown in Table 1. In the notation, the alphabets U and Q represent unidirectional and quasi-isotropic, respectively, and the numerals 8 and 3 stand for T800 and T300 carbon fibers.

3.2 Test Procedure

For the strain gage method, foil gages were glued on both surfaces at midspan. A pair of loading devices were attached to an Instron-type testing machine. These devices were designed so that they realize the pin support. The displacement transducer to measure the deflection at midspan was also attached

Fig.5 Bending strength[1]

as shown in Fig.2. The crosshead speed was 2mm/min. The applied load, surface strains, and deflection were saved in a personal computer with the sampling time of 1 second.

The test procedure and data reduction for the elastica method are almost the same as the case of strain gage method. Only the applied load and the crosshead movement should be measured. Since the deflection is not necessary to measure, the complicated device to measure the deflection (see Fig.2) is not necessary. Also strain gages are not needed.

In addition to these compression bending, conventional four point bending was also done as a reference.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Bending Strength

Three lengths ($L=100, 150, 200\text{mm}$) were selected for compression bending and the width of the specimen, b , was fixed to 15mm. The number of specimens was six for each case.

Since the result was already reported in Ref.[1], only one figure is quoted here. Figure 5 is the case. The major conclusion of this Figure is that for T800 composites (U8 and Q8), the bending strength measured by the present compression bending method is larger than that of four-point bending. For T300 composites (U3 and Q3), no evident difference was observed between the two. Since more advanced composites have been developed, the importance of the present method may increase hereafter. By the way, the failure took place at the compression side for T800 composites whereas T300 composites began to fail from the tension side.

4.2 Bending Modulus

Figure 6 is some examples of the load-deflection curves for U8 specimens with various specimen length. This is the case of strain gage method. It should be noted that test was terminated before the failure because the specimen was supplied to the four-point bending, too. As is shown in this figure, deformation of the specimen starts from the early stage of loading; this is not a pure Euler buckling.

Figure 7 is the load-crosshead movement curves. This figure is drawn for the convenience to understand the applied load in Figs. 3 and 4. At the very beginning of loading, the

Fig.6 Example of load-deflection curves

load did not increase so much regardless the crosshead was moving. This unexpected phenomenon will probably be due to the shape of the groove made in the loading device to insert the specimen. Since the bottom of the groove is semi-circular, the contact to the rectangular end of the specimen is not face contact but line contact which may cause some error. Some clearance of the device might be another reason. Thus modification against the above mismatch has been done to produce Fig.7.

Circles of Fig.3 are the test results for $\delta/L - \lambda/L$. Again the test was stopped before failure. Circles of Fig.4 are also the experimental results. In both cases, the difference between the theory and experiment is small.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between the crosshead movement and the bending modulus measured by two methods for the same coupon. Except for the very beginning, the bending modulus was almost constant. Also the difference between the values of strain gage method and the elastica method was within several percent.

Table 2 summarizes the bending moduli measured by various method. In the four-point bending, the bending modulus was calculated at the early stage of the load-deflection curve (tangent modulus), whereas the secant modulus at somewhat large deflection, say $\lambda/L=0.1$, was taken for the compression bending. Anyway, the difference of the modulus between the four-point

Fig.7 Example of load-crosshead movement curves

Fig.8 Bending modulus vs. crosshead movement

Table 2 Comparison of bending moduli measured by several methods

		4-Point bending (GPa)	Compression bending (GPa)	
			Elastica method	Strain gage method
T 300	U	157.6	146.7	153.6
	Q	70.71	64.80	68.05
T 800	U	129.1	122.2	127.3
	Q	59.02	55.70	58.70
U:Unidirectional		Q:Quasi - isotropic		

bending and the compression bending is small.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a new bending test method named as compression bending was tried. It has been made clear that the present method is superior to the conventional bending test method especially for bending strength.

Efforts were also done to calculate the bending modulus by means of the compression bending. Strain gage method and elastica method were tried. The results showed that the bending modulus can be calculated by the present method.

Both strength and modulus could be measured and therefore, this method may become one candidate for the bending test of advanced composites. Among the two methods, the elastica method will be more convenient because complex device and consuming strain gages are not necessary.

One point to be noted is that we must be careful to cut the end of the specimen. The pin-joint type loading device should be modified to get more reliable data.

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References

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